

Carbon-13 NMR Spectra of Angular and Linear Furanoflavones[†]

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¹³C NMR spectra of four angular furanoflavones, lanceolatin B, karanjin, kanjone and 5-methoxyfuran(8,7-4'',5'')flavone and one linear furanoflavone, pinnatin were analysed and their carbon shifts assigned. Certain distinctive features of similarly substituted angular and linear furanoflavones have been pointed out.

THE occurrence of three new and eight known furanoflavonoids and five other flavonoids in the flowers of *Pongamia glabra* Vent. (Leguminosae) was recently reported by us^{1,2}. To our knowledge, ¹³C nmr spectral analysis of furanoflavonoids has not appeared in the literature till date. The present communication portrays the application of ¹³C nmr spectroscopy† to the major angular furanoflavones, lanceolatin B³ (I), karanjin (II), kanjone (III), 5-methoxyfuran(8,7-4'',5'')-flavone (IV) and the only linear furanoflavone, pinnatin (V), occurring in the flowers of *P. glabra*.

The assignments of the ¹³C chemical shifts (δ_{TMS} , ppm) were based on the examination of the splitting pattern in the single frequency off-resonance decoupled spectra, comparison of the chemical shifts with the previously reported data for flavones³⁻⁵ and furanocoumarins⁶ together with the use of additive substituent parameters^{7,8}. The assigned ¹³C chemical shifts of the furanoflavones (I)–(V) are presented in Table I. The salient features observed are discussed in the sequel.

in the spectrum of the linear furanoflavone (V) the signal for C-4a (having no *ortho* proton) appearing at δ 112.58 and not C-8a was the least intense one. The deshielding of C-8a in (V) by 2-4 ppm relative to those in (I)–(IV) is noteworthy. The chemical shift for the carbonyl of flavones⁴ (~178 ppm) remains almost unaffected by the fusion of the furano moiety to the flavone nucleus. The furan oxygen present on C-7 in the furanoflavones (I)–(V) shields C-4a (*para* position) by ~4 ppm whereas in simple flavones the shielding of C-4a by a 7-methoxy group⁴ is ~6 ppm. It is worthwhile to mention

TABLE I—¹³C CHEMICAL SHIFTS (ppm) OF THE FURANOFLLAVONES (I)–(V)

Carbons	(I)	(II)	(III)	(IV)	(V)
2	162.25	154.25	161.75	159.99	161.01
3	107.67	141.46	106.91	109.43	107.59
4	177.88	174.56	177.47	177.67	178.14
4a	119.14	119.29	119.62	110.02	112.58
5	121.49	121.41	99.64	157.97*	155.51
6	109.83	109.50	143.88	91.77	117.00
7	158.10	157.71	147.75	158.05*	157.83
8	116.94	116.60	116.50	111.03	95.19
8a	150.49	149.60	149.75	151.84	153.43
1'	131.35	130.61	131.39	131.15	131.34
2'	125.88	127.97	125.62	125.71	125.86
3'	128.90	128.29	128.65	128.34	128.76
4'	131.35	130.31	130.98	131.15	131.14
5'	128.90	128.29	128.65	128.34	128.76
6'	125.88	127.97	125.62	125.71	125.86
2''	145.66	145.45	145.57	144.18	145.09
3''	103.96	103.84	104.22	103.82	105.18
OCH ₃	—	59.80	56.00	56.62	61.60

* Assignments may be interchangeable.

In the spectra of the angular furanoflavones (I)–(IV) the signal for C-8a having no *ortho* proton appeared as the least intense one around δ 150 while

here that in furanocoumarins⁶ C-3 is shielded by ~4 ppm by the *para* orientation of the furan oxygen to the acrylic acid portion of the coumarin moiety. The chemical shifts of the carbons of the furano moiety (C-2'' and C-3'' here) are almost similar to those in furanocoumarins⁶. The chemical shifts of the methoxyls in 6-methoxy-angular furanoflavone (III) and 5-methoxy-angular furanoflavone (IV) are close to those observed⁴ in cases of simple 6-methoxyflavone and 5-methoxyflavone respectively. In (III) the shielding effects of 6-methoxyl on the *ortho* carbons C-5 and C-7 are unequal (~22 and ~10 ppm respectively) and are similar to those observed⁴ in case of 6-methoxyflavone. In (IV), the *ortho* carbon C-4a is shielded due to the 5-methoxyl by

†Dedicated, with profound regards, to Professor Nil Ratan Dhar, on the occasion of his 90th birthday in recognition of his contribution to chemistry and service to the nation.

9.1 ppm, comparable to that observed⁴ in case of 5-methoxyflavone. However, in (IV), the other *ortho* carbon C-6 is shielded by ~18 ppm and the *para* carbon C-8 by 5.9 ppm whereas the corresponding carbons in 5-methoxyflavone are shielded⁴ by ~15 ppm and 11.7 ppm respectively. This difference in shielding effects between (IV) and 5-methoxyflavone may be ascribed to the fixation of the 7,8- double bond in (IV) due to the fusion of the furan moiety, thus reducing the electron relay from the methoxyl oxygen to C-8 and resulting in increased electron relay to C-6. In the case of karanjin (II) the signal of the 3-methoxyl appeared at somewhat lower field (~3 ppm) than those of the 5- and 6-methoxyls of (IV) and (III) respectively; further, this 3-methoxyl was found to exert shielding effects of ~3 ppm on the carbonyl shift and of 8 ppm on C-2 carbon shift.

Due to nonavailability of the unsubstituted linear furanoflavone, [furano (6,7-4",5") flavone], the expected ¹³C nmr spectral difference between this linear furanoflavone and its angular isomer (I), arising out of the difference in the sites of the furan ring fusions only, could not be studied. Although the spectrum of the linear monomethoxyfuranoflavone (V) is available, the effect of the methoxy substitution on the linear furanoflavone molecule and its comparison with the same effect in the case of the angular furanoflavone could not be studied. However, some differences are observed when a comparison of the chemical shifts of the angular 5-methoxyfuranoflavone (IV) with those of its linear isomer (V) is made. Thus, C-6 in (IV) is more shielded (by ~3.5 ppm) than C-8 in (V). Again, the methoxyl signal in (V) appeared at a lower field (~5 ppm) than that in (IV); the greater deshielding in (V) may be due to the greater participation of its canonical form in which the aromaticity of the furan ring is restored than the canonical form of (IV) in which the furan aromaticity is lost¹. Similar differences were observed in the ¹H nmr spectra of (IV) and (V)¹. Furthermore, a diagnostic chemical shift difference of C-6 and C-8 in 5-methoxy angular and linear furanoflavones was also observed. Thus, C-6 of (V) resonated at a much lower field (~25 ppm) than that of (IV). Likewise, C-8 of (IV) also resonated at a significantly lower field (~16 ppm) than that of (V). Interestingly, the ring juncture carbon [C-6 in (V) and C-8 in (IV)] is more deshielded. This deshielding can presumably be

attributed to the paramagnetic anisotropic effect of the furan ring on the ring juncture carbon. Moreover, the shielding effect of the 5-methoxyl is expected to be more pronounced at C-6 in (IV) as compared to that in (V) and at C-8 in (V) as compared to that in (IV) owing to the pronounced 7,8- double bond fixation in (IV) and the more electron relay from the methoxyl oxygen to C-8 restoring the aromaticity of the furan ring in (V).

Experimental

The furanoflavones (I)-(V) were obtained from the light petrol and chloroform extracts of the flowers of *P. glabra*^{1,2}: (I) m.p. 137°; (II), m.p. 161°; (III), m.p. 187-88°; (IV), m.p. 176°; (V), m.p. 181°. The carbon-13 nmr spectra of all the compounds were taken in CDCl₃ at 0.25-0.50 molar concentrations with a Varian Associates CFT-20 (20 MHz) spectrometer. The chemical shift and degree of protonation of each carbon were determined by proton noise decoupling and single frequency off-resonance decoupling (SFORD) experiments respectively. The chemical shifts were taken from the computer generated print-out; the actual standard used was the centre line of CDCl₃ which was taken as 76.9 ppm downfield from TMS. Distinction of close resonance signals was done on the basis of qualitative relaxation characteristics.

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